

Pheromone Synthesis. Part-189 Ψ . Synthesis of the Enantiomers of 6-Methyl-3-nonanone, the Female-produced Sex Pheromone of Caddisfly, *Hesperophylax occidentalis*

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Both the enantiomers of 6-methyl-3-nonanone (1), the female-produced sex pheromone of the caddisfly (*Hesperophylax occidentalis*) have been synthesized by starting from the enantiomers of citronellal (2).

In 1996, Bjostad *et al.*¹ isolated and identified the female-produced sex pheromone of the caddisfly (*Hesperophylax occidentalis*) as 6-methyl-3-nonanone (1). They then synthesized (\pm)-1 and its analogs, and found (\pm)-1 to elicit the greatest electroantennographic responses². The absolute configuration of the naturally occurring 1, however, could not be determined. Because bioactivity of a chiral pheromone usually depends on its absolute configuration³, we undertook the synthesis of both (*R*)- and (*S*)-1 so as to clarify the absolute configuration of the natural and bioactive enantiomer.

Scheme 1 summarizes our synthesis of the enantiomers of 1. The enantiomers of citronellal (2, *ca.* 97% e.e.) were chosen as the starting materials due to their commercial availability. (*S*)-Citronellal (2) was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride to give (*S*)-citronellol (3), of which known tosylate 4⁴ was treated with lithium dimethylcuprate to yield the alkene (*R*)-5. Ozonolytic cleavage of (*R*)-5 afforded the known aldehyde (*R*)-6⁵. Treatment of (*R*)-6 with ethylmagnesium bromide furnished a diastereomeric mixture of the alcohol (3*RS*, 6*R*)-7, which was oxidized to give (*R*)-6-methyl-3-nonanone (1), [α]_D²⁵ = -3.12 (CHCl₃). Similarly, (*R*)-citronellal (2) was converted to (*S*)-1, [α]_D²⁶ = +3.07 (CHCl₃). Because there was no step in the present synthesis to deteriorate the enantiomeric purity at the chiral center, the final products (*R*)- and (*S*)-1 were considered to be of *ca.* 97% e.e. like the starting materials. It should be added that the enantiomers of 1 could not be separated by gas chromatographic analysis on a cyclodextrin-derived chiral stationary phase. The overall yield of 1 was 12–18% based on 2 (six steps).

In conclusion, both (*R*)- and (*S*)-1 were synthesized, and they are now under biological evaluation.

Experimental

All b.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra were measured as films for oils on a Jasco A-102 spectrometer, ¹H nmr spec-

Scheme 1 Synthesis of (*R*)- and (*S*)-1 Reagents (a) LiAlH₄, Et₂O (80%), (b) TsCl, C₅H₅N, (c) Me₂CuLi, Et₂O (65% based on 3), (d) i) O₃, MeOH, NaHCO₃, ii) Me₂S (83%), (e) EtMgBr, Et₂O (67%) and (f) Jones CrO₃, MeCO (63%)

tra at 90 MHz on a Jeol EX-90A or at 300 MHz on a Bruker DPX 300 spectrometer, the peak for TMS or solvent (CHCl₃ : δ 7.26) being used as the internal standard, ¹³C nmr spectra at 75.5 MHz on a Bruker DPX 300 spectrometer, solvent peak (CDCl₃ : δ 77.0) being used as the internal standard, and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS-SX102A or a Hitachi M-80B spectrometer. Optical rotations were measured on a Jasco DIP-1000 polarimeter. Refractive indices were measured on an ATAGO Abbe refractometer 1T.

2,6-Dimethyl-2-nonene 5. (R)-isomer : A solution of lithium dimethylcuprate (*ca.* 0.35 *M* in ether) was prepared from a solution of MeLi (1.03 *M* in ether, 400 ml, 412 mmol) and CuI (40.0 g, 210 mmol) in dry diethyl ether (200 ml) in the usual manner. It was added dropwise to a solution of the known (*S*)-4 (41.5 g, 134 mmol)⁴ in dry diethyl ether (130 ml) at -60° under Ar. After stirring overnight at 4° , the mixture was quenched with sat. NH_4Cl aq. and extracted with pentane. The extract was washed with water and brine, dried (MgSO_4) and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was chromatographed over SiO_2 and distilled to give (*R*)-5 (15.5 g, 65% based on (*S*)-3), a colorless oil, b.p. $81-82^{\circ}/34$ Torr; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{26} = -1.96$ (*c* 1.45, CHCl_3); $\eta_{\text{D}}^{23} = 1.4330$; ν_{max} (film)/1670 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ_{H} (90 MHz; CDCl_3) 0.75–1.00 (6H, m, 6-Me, 9-H), 1.00–1.60 (7H, m, 5, 6, 7, 8-H), 1.60 (3H, s, 2-Me), 1.68 (3H, s, 1-H), 1.80–2.10 (2H, m, 4-H), 5.10 (1H, br t, *J* 7.1, 3-H); HRMS *m/z* 154.1710, $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{22}$ requires *m/z* 154.1719.

(*S*)-*Isomer* : In the same manner as described above, (*R*)-4 (19.9 g, 64.2 mmol) was converted into (*S*)-5 (6.39 g, 61% based on (*R*)-3), a colorless oil, b.p. $85-87^{\circ}/41$ Torr; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{23} = +2.02$ (*c* 1.42, CHCl_3); $\eta_{\text{D}}^{24} = 1.4321$. Its ir and ^1H nmr spectra were identical with those of (*R*)-5; HRMS *m/z* 154.1718, $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{22}$ requires *m/z* 154.1719. Due to its volatility no correct combustion analytical data of **5** could be obtained.

4-Methylheptanal 6. (R)-Isomer : Ozone was bubbled into a cooled and stirred suspension of NaHCO_3 (1.80 g, 21.4 mmol) in a solution of (*R*)-5 (13.1 g, 85.0 mmol) in MeOH (240 ml) at -70° to saturation. After flushing off the excess ozone by bubbling N_2 , dimethyl sulfide (8.0 g, 0.13 mol) was added. The mixture was allowed to warm to room temperature with stirring over 3 h. It was then poured into water and extracted with pentane. The extract was washed with water and brine, dried (MgSO_4), and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was distilled to give (*R*)-6 (9.09 g, 83%), a colorless oil, b.p. $78-80^{\circ}/104$ Torr; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -0.86$ (*c* 1.56, CHCl_3); $\eta_{\text{D}}^{24} = 1.4199$; ν_{max} (film) 2730 cm^{-1} (aldehyde C–H), 1725 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ_{H} (90 MHz; CDCl_3) 0.80–1.00 (6H, m, Me), 1.00–1.83 (7H, m, 3, 4, 5, 6-H), 2.41 (2H, br d, *J* 7.4, 2-H), 9.75 (1H, t, *J* 1.9, 1-H); HRMS *m/z* 128.1197, $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$ requires *m/z* 128.1201.

(*S*)-*Isomer* : In the same manner as described above, (*S*)-5 (6.37 g, 41.3 mmol) was converted into (*S*)-6 (4.20 g, 80%), a colorless oil, b.p. $67^{\circ}/97$ Torr; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = +1.10$ (*c* 1.43, CHCl_3); $\eta_{\text{D}}^{23} = 1.4219$. Its ir and ^1H nmr spectra were identical with those of (*R*)-6; HRMS *m/z* 128.1217, $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$ requires *m/z* 128.1201. Due to its volatility no correct combustion analytical data of **5** could be obtained.

6-Methyl-3-nonanol 7. (3 RS, 6R)-Isomer : To a solution of (*R*)-6 (7.62 g, 59.4 mmol) in dry diethyl ether (75

ml), a solution of ethylmagnesium bromide (*ca.* 0.75 *M* in diethyl ether, 110 ml, 83 mmol) was added dropwise at 0° under Ar. The mixture was then quenched with sat. NH_4Cl aq., poured into water and extracted with diethyl ether. The extract was washed with water and brine, dried (MgSO_4) and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was chromatographed over SiO_2 and distilled to give (*R*)-7 (6.32 g, 67%), a colorless oil, b.p. $95-98^{\circ}/12$ Torr (Found : C, 75.45; H, 14.38. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}$ calcd for : C, 75.88; H 14.01%); $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{27} = -0.84$ (*c* 1.46, CHCl_3); $\eta_{\text{D}}^{21} = 1.4363$; ν_{max} (film) 3350 cm^{-1} (O–H); δ_{H} (90 MHz; CDCl_3) 0.80–1.05 (9H, m, Me), 1.10–1.70 (11H, m, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8-H), 1.80 (1H, br s, OH), 3.49 (1H, m 3-H); HRMS *m/z* 158.1673, $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}$ requires *m/z* 158.1669.

(3RS, 6S)-*Isomer* : In the same manner as described above, (*S*)-6 (3.89 g, 30.3 mmol) was converted into (*S*)-7 (2.72 g, 57%), a colorless oil, b.p. $83-85^{\circ}/8$ Torr (Found : C, 75.40, H, 14.14. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}$ calcd. for : C, 75.88; H, 14.01%); $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{24} = +0.79$ (*c* 1.34, CHCl_3); $\eta_{\text{D}}^{24} = 1.4344$. Its ir and ^1H nmr spectra were identical with those of (*R*)-7; HRMS *m/z* 158.1678, $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}$ requires *m/z* 158.1679.

6-Methyl-3-nonanone 1. (R)-Isomer : To an ice-cold and stirred solution of (*R*)-7 (4.44 g, 28.1 mmol) in acetone (16 ml), Jones' reagent (2.69 *M* ; 5.5 ml, 15 mmol) was added dropwise. After stirring for 70 min, NaHSO_3 (2.22 g, 21.3 mmol) was added to the reaction mixture. It was then poured into water and extracted with diethyl ether. The extract was washed with water and brine, dried (MgSO_4) and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was chromatographed over SiO_2 and distilled to give (*R*)-1 (2.77 g, 63%), a colorless oil, b.p. $86-87^{\circ}/14$ Torr; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -3.12$ (*c* 12.1, CHCl_3); $\eta_{\text{D}}^{23} = 1.4258$; ν_{max} (film) 2975 cm^{-1} (C–H), 2875 cm^{-1} (C–H), 1725 cm^{-1} (C=O), 1710 cm^{-1} (C=O), 1460 cm^{-1} (C–H), 1425 cm^{-1} , 1380 cm^{-1} , 1350 cm^{-1} , 1160 cm^{-1} , 1140 cm^{-1} , 1110 cm^{-1} , 980 cm^{-1} , 950 cm^{-1} , 760 cm^{-1} , 740 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (300 MHz; CDCl_3) 0.86 (3H, d, *J* 6.3, 6-Me), 0.88 (3H, t, *J* 7.1, 9-H), 1.05 (3H, t, *J* 7.3, 1-H), 1.05–1.45 (6H, m, 5, 7, 8-H), 1.53–1.68 (1H, m, 6-H), 2.31–2.47 (2H, m, 4-H), 2.44 (2H, q, *J* 7.3, 2-H); δ_{C} (75.5 MHz; CDCl_3) 7.7, 14.2, 19.2, 19.9, 30.7, 32.1, 35.7, 38.9, 40.0, 211.9; HRMS *m/z* 156.1519, $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$ requires *m/z* 156.1513.

(*S*)-*Isomer* : In the same manner as described above, (*S*)-7 (2.98 g, 18.8 mmol) was converted into (*S*)-1 (1.94 g, 66%), a colorless oil, b.p. $81^{\circ}/11$ Torr; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{26} = +3.07$ (*c* 12.1, CHCl_3); $\eta_{\text{D}}^{25} = 1.4252$. Its ir, ^1H nmr, and ^{13}C nmr spectra were identical with those of (*R*)-1; HRMS *m/z* 156.1523. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$ requires *m/z* 156.1513. Due to its volatility no correct combustion analytical data of **1** could be obtained.

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